

INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING FUTURE TEACHERS OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION IN SPECIALTY SUBJECTS.

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Abstract: this article talks about the integrated approach of teaching specialized subjects to future technological education teachers in higher educational institutions and its effectiveness indicators. The article also provides information about the importance of the integration approach in the educational process, its essence today, and the analysis of the important aspects of integration in the conducted scientific research.

Key words: integration, technological education, specialized subjects, teaching, educational process, integrative approach, interdisciplinary relations, approach to integration.

In the 21st century, development and digitalization, attention is paid to education and upbringing based on individual, systematic and modern approaches, and this is reflected in each stage of the educational process, and the results are not long in coming. In particular, today, higher education institutions around the world are testing various experiences in the educational process on the basis of an integrated approach to teaching specialized subjects in the preparation of future technological education teachers for psychological and pedagogical activities.

“Ensure universal, inclusive and equitable quality education and upbringing for all throughout life” as defined in the Education 2030 Declaration adopted by UNESCO Within the framework of the task, systematic work is being organized to improve the professional training of future teachers based on an integrated approach, to use innovative and modern educational technologies in the educational process, to form the competitiveness of personnel based on world experience, and to radically transform their pedagogical activities within the framework of various measures aimed at improving the educational process.

In recent years, our republic has been reforming higher education, creating normative foundations for training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities, independent and creative thinking. “Improving the quality of education, bringing the knowledge and skills of pedagogical personnel to the international level” has been set as a priority task . Accordingly, there is a growing need to develop new creative and pedagogical models of transformation in teaching specialized subjects based on an integrated approach in technological education.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60- On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 , Decree No. PF-6108 dated November 6, 2020 “On measures to develop the spheres of education and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan” , Decree No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019 “On approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” , Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 26, 2022 “On measures to improve the quality of pedagogical education and further develop the

activities of higher educational institutions training pedagogical personnel" PQ-289 and Resolution No. PQ-4623 of February 27, 2020 "On measures for the further development of the field of pedagogical education" The implementation of the tasks set out in the resolutions and other regulatory and legal documents related to this activity is becoming an important task for education, science and innovation.

An integrated system, which is formed in cooperation between the learner and the educator, that is, the educational process is organized based on certain laws and principles.

In the textbook "Methodology of Teaching Specialized Subjects", published by G.K. Hasanova, Z.B. Jalilov, the components of the methodology of teaching specialized subjects are classified as follows:

- goals and objectives of education - educational, educational, developmental, organizational;
- laws and principles of education;
- content of education;
- main and auxiliary forms of organizing education;
- general and special methods of education;
- teaching aids;
- learning outcomes.

In addition to the above points, in particular, in technological education, educational goals are based on the content of the subject, and there is also a goal that guides the profession. Future teachers of technological education are taught that educational goals in teaching specialized subjects are determined based on the essence of the subject and the content of the subject, that is, in addition to the basic educational goals, additional, complementary goals are also taught as a constituent component in the pedagogical process.

There are specific pedagogical aspects of organizing the educational process and teaching specialized subjects. In this regard, the textbook "Pedagogy" presented by V.A. Slastetin and other authors describes the pedagogical process as follows: "The main elements of the pedagogical process: goal, task, means and result. Means in a broad sense include content, form and methods. The driving forces of the pedagogical process are: conflicts between the requirements set and the capabilities of the learner. This same contradiction serves as the main source of development." Accordingly, the basic elements that make up the pedagogical process are of great importance in that they reflect not only the content, but also the methods. Based on this, the "conflict" that arises between the educator and the learner actually serves to improve the effectiveness of the educational process.

The textbook "Methodology of Teaching Specialized Subjects" by A.O. Ashirbayev, E.I. Ruziyev, T.E. Tashimov talks about the importance of choosing teaching methods in teaching specialized subjects, that is, the approach to the educational process: "The choice of teaching methods is of great importance in teaching specialized subjects. After all, the choice expands the teacher's capabilities, and the choice of teaching methods that activate the learning activities of students in teaching and learning is an important pedagogical phenomenon. When choosing and optimally applying teaching methods, the teacher must adhere to certain rules of procedure." Therefore, during our research, we came to the conclusion that it is necessary to pay special attention to the importance of the correct choice of teaching methods and the approach in teaching specialized subjects.

Based on the results of the above analysis, it is clear that special attention should be paid to the training of future teachers of technological education in specialized subjects and the introduction of new approaches. In the process of reviewing several studies conducted in the pedagogical field over the past decade, and taking into account the high effectiveness of the integrative approach to the educational process today, we decided to focus this approach specifically on the stage of training future teachers of technological education.

If we consider integration as a process aimed at connecting the content of different disciplines, combining them, and applying the theoretical knowledge obtained in practice, then we can consider the integrative approach to teaching specialized disciplines as a process of connecting several disciplines or subjects of one discipline in terms of content, stratifying them, and applying them to the process as complementary resources.

Today, we can see that the concept of "integration" is recognized as a leading position in modern education. In pedagogical research, integration is described from the point of view of "integrity, systematization, unity, connection".

In the process of training future teachers of technological education, it is important that several specialized disciplines are taught, and they are integrated or taught systematically. In particular, the technological education direction is on the list of pedagogical directions taught for three academic years, and students go through a process that accumulates 180 credits in total. So, despite the lack of time, it is necessary to organize education based on a full-fledged "efficiency-quality" relationship.

In conclusion, we believe that organizing the process based on an integrative position in education will not only improve the knowledge and skills of the teacher, but also encourage future teachers to organize the process with the formation of their competencies in their future pedagogical activities. In conclusion, today, in a period when modern education is undergoing various research and experiments, we need to pay attention to choosing an optimal educational position and connecting knowledge.

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